

SIGNS AND MEASURES TO PREVENT PEOPLE'S DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

This article sugar diabetes diagnosis and the elderly and the elderly ko'proq to occur causes, issues about the information given. Diabetes I and II type of difference of the opening given. Disease treatment principles and disease complications lit.

These diseases Genetic diseases department mainly substances violation as a result of they come, that is, Carbohydrates violation as a result of Sugar diseases occurrence comes in.

The variety of diseases that occur with disorders of carbohydrate metabolism-is different. In the body of mono-, di, and do your part as a result of gene mutation of enzymes polisaxaridlar parchalovchi sintezida galaktozemiya, fruktozemiya, pentozuriya, sugar is the occurrence of disease and other diseases. Of glycogen to'stay away from carbohydrates and plab and glikogenez - speech to'toe the emergence of diseases from plab while mukopolisaxaridoz'ladi.

Older people among sugar diabetes disease of the main challenges is one. This is the main reason of the great age which go towards the endocrine glands partial atrofiyaga occurs and insulin work out, the activity is reduced. All diabetic patients with 80% to 40 over the age of which increased patients, 20% to 50 years of age over patients up makes.

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Sugar diabetes-this is the amount of sugar in the blood, which is the pathological basis for the disease, because the body o'z does not produce insulin in sufficient quantities to meet the needs of. Saxaroza, lactose, and other carbohydrates by the body, so the types of complex sugars'rilgan from before in the digestive tract enzymes ta'monosaxaridlar to toe in secret'need linadi. Into the body entered so'ng, monosaxaridlar usually the body for important energy sources toe'present glyukozaga becomes. Glucose-this blood flow by transported and

cells by so'rilgan the sugar. Body fat's and protein, and glucose also worked out can. The stomach under the gland), from which is produced the hormone insulin in the blood glucose is the amount of control will.

Blood in the stream of glucose in the stomach under bezini insulin work to motivate. Insulin glucose from the blood to the cells o'the teeth to help will. In cells, glucose is immediately used for energy converted or glucose , you need toe'lguncha fat' or glycogen as it is stored

You in the body of glucose to cells o'- check-in passengers for sufficient quantities of insulin work out or cells insulinga normal answer to give to'xtab if (insulin opposition as referred), blood glucose ko'to be payib and in the cells of glucose enough of diabetes symptoms and complications causing produces.

Sugar diabetes type 2 are granted; I-type insulinga gardenliq – at yuveni diabetes. II - type insulinga gardenliq non – elderly diabetes. Sugar diabetes emergence toe'lish in hereditary factors apart, arterial hypertension, heart coronary diseases, infections, mental trauma, obesity big a role it plays. This syndrome development in the body of absolute or relative insulin insufficiency of chilik with characterized. Elderly people in sugar diabetes o'a worthy distinctive feature, they polidipsiya and poliuriyaning the lack of again the body thief reduction, often urination, skin qichib swelling, purulent diseases of the emergence that is. In nursing in the blood glucose nahorda 8-10 mmo ko'comb if the tiny blood vessels and nerve fibers are damaged, this tissue nutrition and blood with provide a process upset get to come. As a result retinopatiya(ko'z nerve atrophy), nefropatiya (in buyrakda in filtrasiya decrease, kidney failure onset) and the foot at serious complications (wound, gangrena) develops. Keksalarda immunity decrease because of pneumonia, o'tkir respiratory diseases, social and diabetic patients with more severe at night. Especially tuberculosis disease , such patients at soon appear it will. Sugar diabetes ko'pinch obesity with along was yesterday. Sugar diabetes 'tola people at a body weight of normal in the patients than 4 times more occurs. Later appetite o'zgarib, the patient ozadi started and quickly was exhausted. The disease is the clinic og'irlik to looking at light, moderate , heavy and severe type is nadi. Light type – in the blood glucose 7, 77 mmo pm toe'ladi, this diet and ugl whom doing so finds the valley restriction with kifoyalaniadi.

O'far-central heavy - type glucose the amount of 12, 21 mmo pm if, per day at 20-60 TB insulin, diet with sugar or decrease commercial sulfanilamid of the drug for certain is justified. O'gir type – in the blood glucose 12, 21 from mmo than it is, large doses of insulinoterapiya is held. Sugar diabetes treatment, each of a patient's general condition, the disease symptoms, blood, urine analysis, and others depending on what is assigned to it, step by step taking is. Sugar diabetes treatment principles the following activities occurs: ☐ Diet eating to apply to; ☐ Physical exercise with shug'to ullana; ☐ in the blood sugar, the amount of tushuruvchi tablets take to; ☐ Insulin using the treatment. Light type diet apply to recommended it. Again, that said switch ke rakka diet with treatment, the disease of all types is prescribed, carbohydrates, the amount of limit, sufficient amounts of proteins and fats recommended are. Patients 9 diet is prescribed. The daily diet of carbohydrates 50%, protein 30%, fat from 30% to up is. Diet to adhere to should be, otherwise the case out of the new treatments have the effect to give despite the fact that di and this disease because they came to the number of the inner member lines (heart, kidney, nervous system, eyes, bottom, feet and other) serious changes to avoid taken to be maydi. O'central heavy type to the diet available being made in addition to, patients definitely sugar amount to normallashtiruchi drugs to drink they need is. In the blood sugar, the amount of decrease in resurrection ingested the drug upon diabetes, glyunorm, man and biguanidlar work wished. Butamid, siklamid, bukarbon, adebit, glyukofag all among them. Og'ir in the type of the patient without insulin to live can't. Coma and prekoma condition toe'become stand can. Insulin with the treatment of the heart – blood vessels to lack of, coronary diseases gipoglikeymiya to either'l not put should. That said o'teeth needless to sugar of the disease, various complications give with xafli is. Sugar diabetes complication is gipoglikeymik coma, insulin amount increases when injected appear it will. In patients holsizlanish, toe'to shash, trembling, cold sweat click, hunger, head pain, anxiety is observed. In such a case, immediately sweet tea, biscuits, rolls given, intravenous 50 ml 40% li glucose solution will be sent. Sent insulin, the amount of enough toe'in the lmas, a diabetic coma happen to give can. Thus, the substances of the exchange deep stability in out, in the blood keton bodies to'plab and will remain. In patients with toe'to shash, apatiya, uyquchanlik, everything be so, vomiting to, thirst, appetite loss is observed, the mouth aseton smell comes, sometimes from hushi goes. Diabetic coma, insulin is 100 tb, oraganizmning to dehydration against sodium chloride izotonik solution, vitamins will be sent. Summary I say sugar diabetes with og'from riga patients dispenser in track to stand they needed. The nurse in the patient's blood and siydigi in glucose, the amount of the regular check have stood should.

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